

Theme of self in the novel *A House for Mr. Biswas*

T.V.N Swathi , Asst. Professor of English (C), IIT Nuzvid ,Nuzvid,Andhra Pradesh

**Paper Received on 01-12-2022, Accepted on 01-01-2023,
Published on 02-01-23;DOI:10.36993/RJOE.2023.8.1.27**

Abstract: Mr Biswas is brought up in poverty due to his father's sudden death. At a tender age he marries Shama, one of Tulsi's daughters. As he has no home of his own he goes to Tulsi's house to live with Shama. Here he starts fighting for his own identity. In his account of growth of Biswas from childhood to adulthood we see the emerging pattern of his personality in conflict with his society. His heroism becomes plausible because the hero is not self regarding for he is constantly aware of the incompleteness of the self. His indestructibility can be seen on the Tulsi estates while working an overseer. He was of the new generation and his life was therefore diametrically opposite to that of the Tulsi's. A house of his own becomes the focus of his quest for something that will imbue his life with meaning something that will give it permanence and dignity. Mr Biswas's persistent desire to understand life and to assert his identity in a chaotic world was thwarted. Most of Naipaul's protagonists come nearer to the sociologist's view of the self rather than the philosopher's. The prologue of the novel beautifully sums up Mr Biswas having arrived at authentic selfhood and helpfully provides a rationale for his final move. The house is both a reality and the metaphor at the centre of the book.

Keywords: Incompleteness of the self, indestructibility, quest, identity, selfhood,

Mr Biswas is the son of Raghu, an East Indian labourer who dies trying to save his son from a pool into which the boy has not fallen really. With the help of his relations, he is brought up in poverty, tries to live independently by doing some work. First he starts as a sign-painter and develops interest in lettering. For some time he works as a conductor on one of Ajodha's buses. He no longer simply lived. He has begun to wait, not only for love, but for the world to yield its sweetness and romance. It is in this mood of expectation that he goes to Hanuman House at Arwacas and sees Shama.

Mr Biswas is trapped into marrying one of the many daughters of the wealthy Tulsi family in a scene which can be seen as a parody of a Hindu arranged marriage. At a tender age he marries Shama, one of Tulsi's daughters. As he has no home of his own he goes to Tulsi's house to live with Shama. Here he starts fighting for his own identity. The Tulsi home is ruled over by the widowed Mrs Tulsi and her brother-in-law, Seth.

Mr Biswas tries to set up his own with the aid of Tulsis but every attempt ends in failure. For his literary aspirations

to read and write are not an integral part of the independence they offer him as a shopkeeper at the Chase and as a sub-overseer at the Greenvale sugar estate. His sensibility revolts against book-keeping and the squalor in which the labourers live: "In all Mr Biswas lived for six years at the Chase, years so squashed by their own boredom... And at least once a week he thought of leaving the shop, leaving Shama, leaving the children, and taking that road." (Pp.182-83)

In his account of the growth of Biswas from childhood to adulthood we see the emerging pattern of his personality in conflict with his society. Naipaul explores the tensions of an individual trapped in such a society through a series of powerful and evocative metaphors. Biswas' fate defines the limits of possibility. Naipaul sees in the West Indian situation, its positive and its negative extremities. After this and for his characters there is nothing left but flight and denial.

Biswas' heroism becomes plausible because the hero is not self-regarding for he is constantly aware of the incompleteness of the self. He is able to say, "I am not whole" (p.232); and this constitutes his heroism: to go on with the journey through the end is beyond thinking. As a result of reading Dickens, "he was given strength to bear with the most difficult part of his day: dressing in the morning, that daily affirmation of faith in oneself, which at times was for him almost like an act of sacrifice." (p.324)

Mr Biswas' indestructibility can be seen on the Tulsi estates while working as an overseer. He is honest and vulnerable: "And though he continued to solace himself with visions of deserted landscapes of sand and snow, his anguish became specially acute on Sunday afternoons, when fields and roads were empty" (p.235). Naipaul communicates the hero's indestructibility as a part of his vulnerability. Mr Biswas survives not because he is weak, but because he knows he is weak. He develops self-awareness through every experience.

Contrasted with the feudal stasis of the Tulsi family of Hanuman House, Mr Biswas' struggles are an attempt to liberate him from the obsolescence of that world. As Patrick Swinden notes, "Biswas has to settle for a life which is awkwardly shot through with memories of a Hindu past and the complex ambition roused by a modern Westernized present."⁸ "Told against an episodic framework of several houses," A House for Mr Biswas is located solidly in the geography and history of Trinidad and Tobago during the period from 1931 to 1948. One is presented with the details of an almost Dickensian world where colonialism has made children old before they can enjoy their childhood.

Mr Biswas was of the new generation, and his life was therefore diametrically opposed to that of the Tulsis. Bereft of either security or solidity in his family life and feeling responsible for his father's death and his family's misfortune, he was forced to leave his

home at Parrot Trace and become a strafe and wanderer. From the moment he left the house: "He was to be a wanderer with no place he could call his own, ... it seemed to him that he was really alone." (p.401) Certainly, this sense of insecurity is emblematic of the newly emerging social order. Marriage, however, introduced Mr Biswas to the Tulsis of Hanuman House. For him, this liaison represented a transition from instability to stability, from a state of permanent homelessness to an apparently safer haven.

Mr Biswas openly disapproves of many of the Tulsis practices and policies. He even challenges their religious belief and associates with Hindus of another sect with whom the Tulsis disagree. He refuses to feel inferior to the Tulsis, though he has no money to his credit. He upsets the Tulsi applecart unforgivably when he buys Savi (his daughter) his personal Christmas present. He differentiates himself by speaking Creole English in Hanuman House while everyone else speaks Hindi (which Naipaul translates into Standard English); he ridicules Hari, the symbol of religious reverence and ceremony; he sees chaos in their communal family arrangements.

It has been said that "Mr Biswas problem is not just to live, but first of all to make for himself a world to live in."¹⁰ The book makes one understand that the real problems facing such men as Mr Biswas in the emerging colonies of the world "are not only economic and political ones. but also those of creating a

morally coherent environment, a truly sustaining culture of making a world which can be deeply meaningful to those who live in it.¹¹ Moral coherence, meaningfulness-these are what Mr Biswas seeks in life though he is unable to articulate his vague yearnings. But when one day he unthinkingly declares to Bipti, his mother: "I am going to get my own house....." he finds the symbol for his quest. A house of his own, then becomes the focus of his quest for something that will imbue his life with meaning, something that will give it permanence and dignity.

The process of acquiring a house "on the face of the earth" becomes more exciting than the actual ownership of it. The house assumes a greater importance than the people. Even for Mr Biswas' children the house was to provide an ordered world, which was never granted to their father. It was hoped that in this changed environment the children would get an opportunity to discover themselves culturally and spiritually.

Mr Biswas' persistent desire to understand life and to assert his identity in a chaotic world was thwarted. Persons like him cannot be allowed the luxury of stability and identity! It may be noted that he himself is not unaware of his ambivalent position. He tells his son: "I am just somebody. Nobody at all. I am just a man you know." This is obviously, the fate of men like Mr Biswas, who are historically displaced and have the misfortune of living in a derelict land. Society offers very little possibilities to

each one of them, and he has therefore no option but "to balance his personal inadequacies against the contradictions of existence itself."¹²

Mr Biswas' vicissitudes lend a deeper perspective to colonial experiences. He is denied the satisfaction of seeing his aspirations and dreams come true. It is interesting to note that Mr Biswas' eagerness to have a house of his own has an element of self-revelation about it. Naipaul lived in the beginning in the 'big house' owned by his mother's mother in Chaguanas. "It was built in the North Indian style. It had balustrade roof terraces, and the main terrace was decorated at end with a statue of a rampant lion." He was bound to become a 'non-entity' in atmosphere. He remembers: "Growing up within the extended family knowing nothing else, or looking at everything else from the outside, I had no social sense..... And as a result I couldn't enter worlds that were not like mine." Naipaul's last two years in the 'big house' were 'close to a nightmare'. By the time his father managed to buy a house of his own in 1946, when Naipaul was 14, it was already a little late, "By 13 that my childhood was over and I was fully made," adds Naipaul.¹³ His experiences in this respect are thus not different from those of Mr Biswas. The problems of the latter, however, are the problems of the entire West Indian society.

Naipaul's invented country of the East-Indians in West Indies is a symbol of decadent culture and familial

fragmentation on the one hand, and of a personal quest for self-fulfillment and identity on the other. It is a novel, as William Walsh observes: "in the grand manner, deliberate, large in scope, constructing a world with authoritative ease, with a central figure, a biographical line, This is realized in the creative, encompassing metaphor which initiates and sustains the novel."²⁰

Most of Naipaul's protagonists come nearer to the sociologist's view of the self rather than the philosopher's. 'Self' in this sense is an entity that arises and develops in the process of an individual's social experiences and activities. Port of Spain helps Biswas to bring about a re centering of the displaced impulse and the restructuring of his self. The urge to have his own house strengthened by his awareness of his children's emotional needs now comes upon him in a big way. Going in for a house of his own is for Mr Biswas a kind of investment in the future, in the continuity of his own self after his death. The Epilogue at one point tells us: "Living had been a preparation, a waiting and so the years had passed; and now there was nothing to wait for." (p.586) This could sound pretty gloomy but pat come the words: "Except the children." (p.586) This clearly indicates his attainment of authentic selfhood. His investing in the children's happiness is a sign of his having travelled a long way from the restlessness and lack of focus of the Tulsi dominated days. How much the house in Sikkim Street means to the

children, despite all its shortcomings can be seen in.

Soon, it seemed to the children that they had never lived anywhere but in the tall square house in Sikkim Street. "From now on their lives would be ordered, their memories coherent." (p.581) In his own house, Biswas' relationship with Shama too undergoes a positive transformation: "He didn't now care to do anything against his wife's wishes.... Shama had learned a new loyalty to him and to their children; away from her mother and sisters, she was able to express this without shame, and to Mr Biswas this was a triumph almost as big as the acquiring of his own house." (p.8) "The Prologue' of the novel beautifully sums up Mr Biswas' having arrived at authentic selfhood and helpfully provides a rationale for his final move. It refers to: "He thought of the house as his own, though for years it had been irretrievably mortgaged.....to hear no noises except that of the family, to wander freely from room to room...." (p..8) And the rationale "How terrible... unaccommodated." (p.14)

Mr Biswas is aware that not to have this house would have been at negation of his worth as a human being. The house is both a reality, and the metaphor at the centre of the book. It is given a depth of meaning which transcends the physical object, without effacing its solidity. Naipaul describes the book as "the story of a man's search for a house and all that the possession of one's own house implies" (Writing A House for

Mr Biswas, p.22). The house is made to imply a great deal. Critics have noted the allusion to King Lear in the weighty reflection in the above passage.

The marriage of Mr Biswas and Shama is being pulled in opposite directions. Mr Biswas feels happy only when he has succeeded in tearing himself away from the Tulsi grip; the marriage is happy for Shama only when she is functioning as a part of the Tulsis, bearing children, paying visits, sharing grief and joy with the rest. Each time a child is born or something significant happens, the Tulsis reach out, and Mr Biswas draws away. He warns his children against the Tulsis, urges them to rebel; and he considers himself a failure and confides to Anand, his son: "I don't want you to be like me." "Anand understood. Father and son, each saw the other as weak and vulnerable and each felt a responsibility for the other, or responsibility which, in times of particular pain, was disguised by exaggerated authority on the one side, exaggerated respect on the other." (p.338) He deeply feels whenever he hears his daughter speak in the manner of Mrs Tulsi or Shama.

Shama gradually begins to share the economic burden of the house by her various schemes to earn money, and tries to help Biswas "to paddle his own canoe," and learns to depend on him instead of running off to her mother as she always did earlier throughout the marriage indeed, Shama develops into something more like a wife than Mr

Biswas could have expected of a Tulsi daughter: "It gave Mr Biswas some satisfaction that in the circumstances Shama did not run straight off to her mother to beg for help. Ten years before that would have been her first thought. Now she tried to comfort Mr Biswas, and devised plans on her own." (p.7)

Events at the chase had made it clear that the spiritual aloneness of the man is heightened rather than relieved by the solid presence of his conventional wife.

The best summing up of Naipaul's extraordinary achievement in his handling of the theme of selfhood in *A House for Mr Biswas* comes from William Walsh, a perspective critic of Naipaul's work, "The members of the community in *A House for Mr Biswas*.... carry about them... the indelible mark of the slave... unnecessary man. Mr Biswas constructs the proof of his necessity in both a comic and a most moving way... he becomes a model of man just as the history and situation which formed him are seen to be a metaphor of the process which constitutes any man."²⁶

A House for Mr Biswas, then has universality as well as contemporaneity. It spares nothing in judgment, neither in

representation nor reaction. And the whole matter of the novel is informed with a fullness of human sympathy. The important thing to note is that the deficiencies, the pretensions and cruelties of the society which Mr Biswas is caught in are recorded as effects of our common humanity, not as the operations of an alien or inferior nature. That, in itself, is a great triumph for the novelist. It makes his artistic vision remarkably inclusive and gives to *A House for Mr Biswas* a unique position with in his own work.

References

- Autobiography, given in *Gentlemen* (Feb. 1984) pp.46-49.
- Bernard Krikler (Citing Dan Jacobson), "V.S.Naipaul's *A House for Mr Biswas*", *The Listener*, 13 February 1964, p.270.
...Ibid, p.271.
- Landeg White, *V.S.Naipaul: A Critical Introduction* (London, 1975) p.92.
- Swinden, *The English Novel*, p.223.
- Walsh, *V.S.Naipaul* (Edinburgh: Oliver & Boyd, 1973), p.30.
- William Walsh, *V.S.Naipaul* (Oliver and Boyd, 1973), pp.30-31.

How to cite this article?

T.V.N Swathi "Theme of self in the novel *A House for Mr. Biswas*" *Research Journal Of English*(RJOE)8(1),PP:23-27,2023, DOI:10.36993/RJOE.2023.8.1.27